

Effect of a Stochastic Potential in Bound Quantum Mechanics Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 14, 2020

In a previous note (1), we examined the effects of postulating that: $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. This is a Fourier expansion, but we argued it exists for physical reasons i.e. at different times, forces corresponding to different $V_k \exp(ikx)$ pieces i.e. $-d/dx V_k \exp(ikx)$ act on a quantum particle. If one considers $k/-k$, the force is proportional to $\sin(kx)$ if $V(k) = V(-k)$ which may be positive or negative in different x regions even though $-d/dx V(x)$ may be strictly positive. Thus, for an average flow in one direction (caused by $-d/dx V(x)$), there may be pockets of force which act in the forward or negative direction. (One has to keep in mind that some averaging over time is being done.)

We also noted that $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ and so $P(p/x) + P(-p/x)$ is proportional to $\cos(px)$ if $a(-p) = a(p)$. This too may be positive or negative leading to $p^*p/2m [P(p/x) + P(-p/x)]$ being positive or negative in different regions. Thus, if one calculates the average kinetic energy at x : $\sum_p p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, some $p/-p$ pairs contribute "negative" kinetic energy. It seems there should be a physical explanation. In (2), we argued that the bound state Schrodinger equation was equivalent to a hydrodynamical equation if one replaces spatial density with $W(x)$, the wavefunction. Thus, it seems negative contributions to average kinetic energy at x and also momentum "pockets" with the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ which are negative for certain x ranges, might be thought of as being due to non-average motion or acceleration in the opposite direction of the average motion dictated by $-d/dx V(x)$. I.e. the positive/negative forces of the $V_k \exp(ikx)$'s stir up reverse motion which may be seen as "particles" and "kinetic energy" leaving the forward flow. This, we argue, may account for negative contributions to local spatial density and negative kinetic energies. Later, the particle reverses direction or acceleration and contributes to the forward flow what was lost in a different x region. Thus, there may be a buildup of spatial density and kinetic energy density in different regions. In this note, we try to examine this in more detail and also consider an interpretation of the density average $W^*(x)$ Operator $W(x)$ in this model.

Negative Kinetic Energy Contributions to Averages

If a quantum particle is subject to hits from force terms $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ which act at different times, one may see that using $k/-k$ with $V(k) = V(-k)$ (as an example) yields a force (averaged at two times) proportional to $\sin(kx)$. Thus, the force may be positive in one x region and negative in another, even though the average force $-d/dx V(x)$ is strictly positive.

In a classical problem, a bound particle moves (for example) in the forward direction, slows down and turns around and then moves in the negative direction. There is a physical flow. In quantum mechanics, one has a momentum distribution at point x with $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ which contains both positive and negative momenta, but there is an average $p = \sum_p p P(p/x)$ which has a specific direction at each x . Specific $P(pi/x) + P(-pi/x)$, however, may be

proportional to $\cos(px)$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$. Thus, one has flow (for example) to the right at x , but negative contributions to a kinetic energy average from: $\frac{p^2}{2m} [P(p/x)+P(-p/x)]$. How can one have a negative kinetic energy contribution? First, we have argued in a previous note (3), that the form $V(x)=\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ forces $P(p/x)$ to have the oscillatory form $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Thus, it seems it is the fact that $V(k)\exp(ikx) + V(-k)\exp(-ikx)$ may yield forces to the right or left, that leads to particle motion or acceleration to the right or left even though $-d/dx V(x)$ is in one direction. (Note: acceleration is related to changes in $P(p/k)$ not to p changing from x_1 to x_2 as in classical physics.) This forward/negative motion or acceleration is different for different p values and it may be noted that: $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) =$ Classical kinetic energy at each x point. Thus, an interpretation is needed. If one considers a quantum system as a hydrodynamical one (see (2)), then having some p momenta at x move or accelerate “backwards” seems to give the impression of particles and kinetic energy lost from the forward motion at x . We argue this may be a physical way of interpreting such negative terms which follow directly from forces pieces acting in the negative direction in certain regions even though $-d/dx V(x)>0$ for a particular problem.

If $\frac{d}{dx} P(p/x) - \frac{d}{dx} P(-p/x)$ is negative in a region, there is a negative contribution to the average p which tends to slow the average down. For a classical gas, one might expect $\frac{d}{dx} P(p/x) - \frac{d}{dx} P(-p/x) = 0$. Thus, the negative $\frac{d}{dx} P(p/x) + \frac{d}{dx} P(-p/x)$ seems to be related to motion (or acceleration) opposite to the average suggested by $-dV/dx$.

The next question is whether this idea may be applied to a physical observable, as one may not measure the average kinetic energy at x . A physical observable which also exhibits negative and positive pockets at different x is the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$. In (3), we argued that the relative probability to have a particle with momentum p at x is $a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In a Δx , it receives one hit from a $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ and changes momentum to $p+k=p_2$, where the relative probability to have p_2 is $a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$. Thus, one considers all possible combinations and adds to obtain a spatial density:

$$\sum_{i, j} a(p_i) \exp(ip_i x) a(p_j) \exp(ip_j x) \quad ((1))$$

At first, one may ask why it is necessary to consider two momenta. If one wishes to calculate the average kinetic energy at x , all that is needed is $P(p/x)$ i.e. $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Only one $a(p)$ appears. At a point $x+\Delta x$, the same set of p values appear, but the probability changes and this is linked to average acceleration. For the stochastic picture, the product of relative weights captures the different transitions. Summing over all yields all possible scenarios of having a particular p_i which then changes to p_j . $a(p_i)\exp(ip_i x)$ is a relative weight. Its modulus does not change with x , but average values (with say $-p_i$) do. The product terms in ((1)) may also be averaged with their negatives i.e. p_i+p_j and $-p_i-p_j$ changes in sign with x . If one considers p_i+p_j and $-p_i-p_j$ and $a(p)=a(-p)$, there are pockets of $\cos((p_i+p_j) x)$ and so x regions for which the p_i+p_j combination is negative i.e. removes density. How does one remove density? First, a particle moving or accelerating backwards at x when the average flow is forward may be seen as “removing” density. Here, the average flow is created by averaging various momenta at x at different times. The p_i momentum only appears at one time and $-p_i$ at another. Nevertheless, on average they may yield a $\cos(p_i x)$ term if $a(p)=a(-p)$. Mathematically,

$a(p_i) \exp(i p_i x) a(p_j) \exp(i p_j x)$ is a product of relative probabilities (occurring one after the other at a time t) and the same expression with $-p_i, -p_j$ at another time, but is still a probability itself. In equilibrium (i.e. a bound state), one wishes to know how this probability changes in different x regions. If it becomes negative, we argue it behaves opposite to the hydrodynamical flow and removes probability from a region. Later, in another region, this "removed" density appears (because it is now moving or accelerating in a forward direction) augmenting the density there. Thus, one may have regions with high spatial density and others with lower. In fact, one may have spatial density values oscillate in x with high densities regions followed by low followed by high etc. We argue this is all caused by the force being positive/negative in different x regions although always adding to give $-d/dx V(x)$ at each x .

Another way to consider this is the following. Examine a single term of ((1))

$$a(p_i) \exp(i p_i x) a(p_j) \exp(i p_j x) \quad ((2a))$$

Next, sum over all initial p_i to obtain: $W(x) a(p_j) \exp(i p_j x)$. Do the same thing with:

$$a(-p_i) \exp(i -p_i x) a(p_j) \exp(i -p_j x) \text{ to obtain } W(x) a(-p_j) \exp(i -p_j x) \quad ((2b))$$

If one adds ((2a)) and ((2b)), one obtains: $W(x) a(p_j) 2 \cos(p_j x)$ if $a(p)=a(-p)$.

Thus, if $\cos(p_j x)$ is negative, one has a negative contribution to spatial density and here p_j applies to only one momentum. Thus, one may think of a particle with $p_j/-p_j$ as moving or accelerating in the opposite sense to $-dV/dx$. In this case, however, spatial density is a physical observable and so the unusual back/forth motion or positive/negative acceleration (manifested through $P(p/x)$) creates direct physical effects.

Spatial Density Averages

In the previous section, we argued that spatial density is a physical observable directly affected by pockets of motion or acceleration opposite to the average motion dictated by $-dV/x$. We argued that using $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ allows for positive/negative forces to arise at a given x at different times even though the overall sum is $-dV/dx$.

In quantum mechanics, spatial density averages i.e. $W^*(x)W(x) f(p) P(p/k)$ or $W^*(x)W(x) g(x)$ where f and g are two functions, often appear. We wish to examine this average in terms of the microscopic picture given above.

Consider kinetic energy in 1 dimension first i.e.:

$$\text{Integral } dx \text{ Sum over } KE(x) W^*(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p p^*p/2m a(-p)a(p) = \text{Sum over } p p^*p/2m P(p/x) P(x) \quad ((3))$$

Where $KE = \text{Sum over } p a(p) p^*p/2m \exp(ipx) /W(x) = \text{Sum over } p p^*p/2m P(p/x)$

Thus, one multiplies physical spatial density (which represents a time average) by the average kinetic energy at x (also a time average) to obtain the overall kinetic energy in the system. One may rewrite ((3)) as:

$$\int dx \sum_{\text{over } p} W^*(x) \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) = \sum_{\text{over } p} \frac{p^2}{2m} a(-p)a(p) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one considers a particle with momentum p at x and uses this in the calculation of $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ even though there will be a change within Δx , namely there will be a force hit changing the momentum to $p+k$. In classical physics, however, one does a similar thing because one uses velocity(x) in a region Δx even though the particle is accelerating in this region. What is interesting about ((4)) is that mixed $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ terms contribute to the kinetic energy density at each x , yet when one takes the integral over dx only $a(-p)a(p)$ terms remain. To see this more clearly, consider a p and $-p$ term from $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy at x) for $a(-p)=a(p)$:

$$2 a(p) \cos(px)/W(x) \text{ multiplied by: } a(p) 2 \cos(pj x) W(x)$$

Thus, there are negative contributions from both $\cos(px)$ and $\cos(pj x)$ in certain x regions due to backward motion or negative acceleration. Due to the fact that $\cos(px)$ and $\cos(pj x)$ are orthogonal for p not equal to p_j , these cancel overall over all x . For $p=p_j$, one has a contribution over all x , because the product of two negative signs in the negative x region is positive. One $\cos(px)$ represents the backward flow in the $KE(x)$ average, the other a part of the density at x due to the backward flow. Thus, not all backward flow terms disappear. For $p=p_j$, the backward flow is as important as the forward. For p not equal to p_j , the local effect is important, but the overall effect (integrated over all x) is 0.

Next, consider: $\int dx V(x) W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(-p) \sum_{\text{over } k} V_k a(p-k)$. This shows an interaction or coupling occurs between $V(x)$ and $W(x)$, with resulting terms associated with $\exp(ipx)$ linking to $\exp(-ipx)$ from $W^*(x)$. This is linear algebra i.e. the dot product of two vectors $W^*(x)$ and $V(x)W(x)$ because an $\exp(ipx)$ orthonormal basis is used.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that negative contributions to average kinetic energy at a point x i.e. $KE(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx)/ W(x)$ (take p and $-p$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ to get $\cos(px)$) have physical meaning. In particular, we argue the particle is moving backwards or accelerating in a backward direction when $-dV/dx$ indicates an average acceleration forward. The backward motion or acceleration is due to the fact that $-d/dx [V_k \exp(ikx) + V_{-k} \exp(-ikx)]$ may be positive in one x region and negative in another (if $V_k=V_{-k}$ etc). (Overall, this backward and forward motion cancels when all of the $V_k \exp(ikx)$ pieces are added to yield $V(x)$). Thus, the force components which add to give $-dV/dx$ may yield positive or negative hits even though the sum yields only positive hits. Given that different $V_k \exp(ikx)$ pieces act at different times, there are kinematical consequences to “backwards” motion or acceleration. For example, if there is average forward flow and some momentum pockets move backwards, it is as if matter and

kinetic energy are being removed from a region x . This removal of matter may seem like an academic issue in the calculation of $KE(x)$, but in the calculation of $W^*(x)W(x)$, the spatial density, it is not because spatial density is apparently a physical observable which may be measured using soft measurements. Thus, backward-forward movement or acceleration may give rise to high and low spatial density regions. Even when calculating density averages using $g(x) W^*(x)W(x)$ or $f(p) a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) W^*(x)W(x)$, integration over dx (1 dimension) ensures a negative sign from $2\cos(px)$ arising from $f(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ for $p/-p$ which is multiplied by a negative sign from $a(p)\cos(px)^2 W(x)$ from $W^*(x)W(x)$. Thus, the backwards motion or acceleration contribute the same as the positive ones for terms with the same p . If the p values are different, there are regions of positive and negative contributions to the energy which ultimately cancel over all x , but which are important to the value of local kinetic energy density $KE(x)W^*(x)W(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Effect of a "Stochastic" Potential in Bound State Quantum Mechanics Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Mechanics and Hydrodynamics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Joint Conditional Probability and Bound Quantum Density (preprint, zenodo, 2020)